

**Madan Bhandari Technological University
Development Board
(MBTU DB)**

**Strategic Proposal for Developing
Madan Bhandari Technological University**

Prepared by:

Madan Bhandari Technological University

Development Board

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra

Baisakh, 25, 2079

Madan Bhandari Technological University
(MBTU)
DECLARATION

I, hereby declare that this study entitled "**Strategic Proposal for Developing Madan Bhandari Technological University**" is based on several scholars review and work. I have consulted and prepared it.

Signature:

Prepared by: **Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra**

Date: **Baisakh, 25, 2079**

मदन भण्डारी प्रौद्योगिक विश्वविद्यालय पूर्वाधार निर्माण विकास समिति
Madan Bhandari Technological University Development Board

APPROVAL

This is to certify that the report entitled "**Strategic Proposal for Developing Madan Bhandari Technological University**" prepared and submitted by **Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra**, is in accordance of MBTUDB Terms of Reference.

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Sincerely,

Dr. Anjay Kumar Mishra

Table of Content

1.	Introduction	1
2.	Background/Context	2
3.	The Concept of Technological University	3
4.	Size of the Institution	4
5.	Entry Requirement	4
6.	Educational Areas	4
7.	Proposed Academic Programs	5
8.	Infrastructures	6
8.1	Class Rooms and Library	6
8.2	Laboratory Class rooms	6
8.3	Workshop Rooms	6
8.4	Administrative Building	7
8.5	Other Facilities	7
9.	Teachers and Staff	8
10.	Tentative Estimate for Overall Physical Infrastructure Development	9
11.	Salary and Allowances for Faculty and Staff	10
12.	Income from Students' Fees	11
13.	Conclusion	12

Madan Bhandari Technological University Development Board (MBTU DB)

Strategic Proposal for Developing Madan Bhandari Technological University

1. Introduction

For producing academically sound and technologically competent high level skilled workforce within the country that could contribute to socio-economic development and improving the quality of life of Nepalese people, the need of a Technological university in the country was felt since more than two decades. Realizing this need, the Government of Nepal has formed Madan Bhandari Technological University Development Board (MBTU DB) on 19 Shrawan, 2077 to carry out the preparatory activities for the establishment of the University. The preparatory work includes land acquisition, formulation of university draft Bill, preparation of master plan, preparation of draft syllabus and student's enrollment plan, preparation of professors and researcher/teachers' roster, preparation of faculties and laboratory equipment list, detail operation plan of university, preparation of physical, legal & institutional infrastructure of the university.

The Government has mentioned in its plan and program of physical year 2077/078, article no. 68 that the necessary preparatory work for the establishment and operation of Madan Bhandari Technological University will be completed. In order to implement the stated policy and program of the government, some budget was allocated from the budget speech of 2077/078, article no.175, for the preparation of documents and legal structure of the university operation.

The university is expected to play an important role for industrial development, productivity improvement and to improve the overall prosperity of Nepalese people by providing relevant, meaningful and practical technology-based education of high standard. The university will be a leading technological university in Nepal offering world-class programs in various technological areas needed for the development of Nepalese economy. The graduates of the University are expected to be innovative, research oriented and capable of providing services in the national and international competitive labor market. The proposed Technological University will (a) equip Nepalese people with advanced technological knowledge, skills, attitudes and sound research foundation, (b) prepare men and women needed for the industrial and economic development of Nepal, and (c) engage in research and development activities to explore meaningful and useful technologies to improve productivity and income of enterprises, and (d) to provide career pathways for the graduates of technical and vocational education. The proposed technical University is also expected to provide ripple effect to enhance income and earning of communities and general public through continuous research and development in the technological program areas that will be offered by the University. This proposal presents the context, rational, purpose and objectives, programs, benefits, and beneficiaries and other conceptual description of the project.

2. Background/Context

Nepal is known to be the most beautiful countries in the world. It has been gifted by the mother nature with natural beauty with pristine land, white Himalayas, clear lakes, clean air, blue sky, white clouds, and white water. The altitude of the country ranges from 60 m above sea level to the highest pick on earth, Mt, Everest at 8848 (8852) meter, all within the aerial distance of 150 km, with climatic conditions from subtropical to arctic. Nowhere in the world is there such a great variation. Travelling in the hilly region, one can feel differences in every 100 meter walk up or down in the mid-hills of Nepal. This beautiful country could not be a poor country.

But,unfortunately the problem of poverty is widespread in Nepal. It has estimated that around 11.2% (2020- worldbank.org –retrieved on 18 January 2020) of the country’s population lives below poverty level. Although poverty is the result of multiple factors, the basic causes are: rapid growth of population, poor infrastructure, lack of excess to education, unemployment and endemic underemployment.

Although there are abundant of natural resources and high potential for economic development, Nepal remained as a country of low economic growth. With the per capita income of about \$1115 US, (2020) which is very low among the South Asian Countries. Adult literacy rate 67.9% and female literacy rate 59.7%, and life expectancy of Nepal is 71.17(2021), which is improving gradually every year.

The agriculture sector in Nepal employs more than 64.54% (2020) of the labor force and contributes 26.5% of the Gross Domestic Products (GDP). However, the GDP contribution of the agricultural marketplace is very low and is still declining.

Unemployment rate in Nepal was found 1.47% in 2020. Underemployment is a more serious problem than unemployment. In order to improve employment situation in Nepal, policy makers have emphasized technical education. Technical education both in the public and private sector is expected to support various types of technical training programs to improve productivity and competitiveness of Nepalese workforce both in the local and foreign labor markets.

The main reason of poor economic performance in Nepal are weak technological knowledge base, stagnation in the growth of business and industries, inability of properly utilizing natural resources and prolonged conflict and disturbance. But the time is favorable now for Nepal to make up of the lost opportunities and speed up the process of national development.

There are some positive aspects that contribute to speeding the process. Some of these aspects are (a) the international trade and market share of Nepalese products is gradually increasing, (b) employment opportunities for Nepalese workforce having technological knowledge and skills has been dramatically increasing (c) there is high potential for creating and expanding small enterprises for rapid economic growth, (d) there is abundant of natural and human resources that can be transformed into productivity improvement and economic development. Some of the biggest roadblocks in harnessing these opportunities are the inadequate knowledgebase, lack of technological research and innovation, inadequate qualified technological experts who can help to transfer technologies to the enterprise level, and budgetary constraints in addressing the specified constraints.

Nepal has three types of human resource development challenges: (a) development of employment-based skills among unemployed/ underemployed masses to increase the employment opportunities for individuals and supply basic and mid-level skilled workforce needed for the business, industry and service sector development; (b) imparting skills for the development and expansion of small enterprises leading to employment generation (c) prepare high level world-class technological workforce who can harness the opportunities from globalization and liberalization of economics and support the enterprises to introduce innovative and marketable products and service through on-going research and development activities. The highly competitive workforce would not only help to boost the national economy but also take advantage from the growing economy of neighboring countries and abroad. This scenario builds the strong justification for developing a leading technological university of its kind that supports to address the human resource development challenges stated above.

3. The Concept of Technological University

The proposed Madan Bhandari Technological University, named after the great visionary leader of Nepal late Madan Bhandari, will be a reality of wishful expectation of many political leaders, technocrats and academicians of Nepal. The University will be functioning with high-level technological innovation and research offering various programs of technological importance for the economic development of Nepal. The University will provide educational programs in relevant technologies of various types and levels with exceptional quality, strong linkages with national economy and labor market, and contribution to the overall transformation of society through technological knowledge and competence. The university will be guided with a VISION- “To become a leading Technological University at the cutting edge of knowledge that produces world class researchers, technologists and innovative leaders committed and competent for building prosperous Nepal where citizens enjoy a life of greater security, well-being and personal dignity”. In order to translate this vision into reality the university will plan to develop technological education system grounded with national values in agricultural and agro forestry-based, engineering, information communication technologies and technologies related to service occupations with a view to prepare qualified and competent human resources needed for national development and societal needs and requirements.

The Technological University will also focus its educational and research programs for the development and expansion of small enterprises not only in the urban centers but also in the rural areas for the purpose of generating employment and earning opportunities for deprived people. The proposed University will also provide the career development opportunities for the graduated of technical schools and polytechnics. The current programs of Technical schools and polytechnic institutes will be strengthened along with the development of a university with a established strong network with the feeder institutes and other national and international universities. The University will develop innovative prototypes, test them in community and disseminate them to the people targeting to raise the economic condition of general public.

The major strategies of the Technological University will be as follows:

- Development of fundamental and applied research for technological development and advancement;

- Formation and development of research and educational institution;
- Collaboration with the leading scientific, educational, and industrial centers and the communities to promote relevancy and quality.
- Motivation of students, teachers, and the other employees to integrate traditional academics values and entrepreneurial ideas;
- Harmonious development of an individual and specialists capable of leadership and effective teamwork, ready to succeed in the conditions of today's competitive environment;
- Providing life-long training and showing the pathway to a successful technical career with strong orientation to psychosocial dimension.

4. Size of the Institution

For sustainability and cost efficiency reasons as well as for meeting the very large number of technical manpower required for development activities, the proposed technological university will have an enrollment capacity of 480 students per year in the initial phase. At full phase running of this size, total number of students will be 1920. Enrollment capacity of the university will be increased as per need in the future expansion stages. It is envisioned that short duration training programs also will be offered mainly during morning, evenings, weekends and semester brakes. The University will be preparing around 5000 technologists and researchers each year in various technological areas of economic importance in Nepal at its full-fledged operation in the future.

5. Entry Requirement

One of the objectives of the university is to provide carrier pathways for the graduates of technical and vocational schools, and polytechnic institutions. The entry level for regular technical education in the polytechnic institutions and technological colleges will be secondary or higher secondary level general or technical education or equivalent qualification determined through cognition and skill test (Diploma or 12th Grade pass). In all cases an entrance test will be administered to ensure academic capabilities, prior knowledge and gain further information for selection purpose.

For short duration technological training programs meant for meeting specific local employment, the entry requirement will be set according to the academic foundation needed to succeed in the training. It is likely that in many cases this will be for people who have not completed high school education. Again, to allow as broad opportunity for access as possible for skill workers and technological workforce to advance their skills or pursue higher education with adequate provisions for preparations or bridge course. An entrance test will normally be administered for entry into the degree offering educational programs.

6. Educational Areas

Specific technological areas will be fixed after having a detailed need assessment of government projects, public, private and industrial sectors. However, the university shall cover wider

disciplines of; Engineering, Health Science, Agriculture and Animal Science, Forestry & Herbal Science and Natural Sciences. The major focus will be towards engineering and technology.

Based on the survey of the labor market and future demands, the university develops faculty, departments, and research centers to offer undergraduate and graduate level educational programs.

At the initial stage of the university, following ten selected programs will be launched at bachelor level which are explained in detail below.

7. Proposed Academic Programs

Table 1: Ten Bachelor Programs and Student Intake Size

S.N.	Programs	Intake			Starting Year	Total Students
		Regular	Paying	Total		
					2080	
1	Construction Technology	10	38	48		192
2	Mechanical & Automation Engineering	10	38	48		192
3	Mechatronics	10	38	48		192
4	Forestry and Wood Technology	10	38	48		192
5	Agroforestry	10	38	48		192
6	Agriculture Technology	10	38	48		192
7	Livestock and Veterinary Technology	10	38	48		192
8	Medical Technology*	10	38	48		192
9	Clinical Technology	10	38	48		192
10	Himalaya Technology	10	38	48		192
	Urban Development					
	Industrial Biotechnology					
	Software Engineering					
	Mining and Metallurgy					
	Dairy Technology					
	Food Technology					
	Nursing and Hospital Management					
		100	380	480		1920

* General, Radiotherapy, Medical Electronics are three scope area of medical technology. Depending upon need assessment final reports, all three could be started together.

After the start of all above programs there will be 480 students' intake per year. Among them 100 students will get scholarship and tuition fee waiver as regular student and 380 will be in the category of paying students.

8. Infrastructures

8.1 Class Rooms and Library

As per the basic norms of NEC, required floor area for class rooms and library rooms for 48 students is 526 m² which is given in table 2 below.

Table 2: Required Size of Classrooms and Library

SN	Categories	Space for 48 students (m ²)
1	Theory class	72
2	Tutorial class	60
3	Drawing class	144
4	Library	250
	Total	526

8.2 Laboratory Class rooms

For basic laboratories of different bachelor's degree programs, total number of 47 rooms with floor area 4130 square meter is required which is given below in table 3.

Table 3: Required Number of Rooms with Sizes for Laboratory Class

SN	Categories	Required rooms	Space for 48 students (m ²)	Total required size (m ²)
1	General lab	8	65.62	525.00
2	Civil Eng. lab	11	54.55	600.00
3	Mechanical lab	5	183.00	915.00
4	Computer lab	6	60.00	360.00
5	Agriculture lab	6	65.62	393.75
6	Electronics lab	5	115.20	576.00
7	Architecture lab	6	126.67	760.02
	Total	47	670.67	4129.82

8.3 Workshop Rooms

Number of class rooms and workshop space for different programs is as estimated in table 4 below.

Table 4: Number of Rooms with Sizes for Workshop

SN	Categories	Required rooms	Space for 48 students (m ²)
1	Fitting and bench works	1	264
2	Welding shops	1	
3	Sheet metal shop	1	
4	Machine shop	1	
5	Smithy shop	1	
6	Foundry shop	1	

7	Total	1	264
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8.4 Administrative Building

As per the basic norms and standards, rooms and space for different administrative facilities requires floor area of 1677 square meter which is given in table 5.

Table 5: Number of Rooms with Sizes for Administrative Facilities

Categories	Required Rooms	Required size (m ²)
Vice chancellor	2	40
Rector	1	20
Registrar	1	20
Dean	2	40
Campus Chief	1	20
Asst. Campus Chief	3	45
Head of departments	7	105
Administration Section	3	60
Account Section	3	45
Examination Section	3	60
Procurement Section/ Main store	3	45
Liaison office room	1	15
Reception lounge	1	20
Registration/Record Room	1	20
Prof/Associate Professor Room	6	528
Teachers Room	6	534
Department offices	6	60
Total	50	1677

8.5 Other Facilities

Under this category for different activities, number of rooms, required size and purpose is given in table 6.

Table 6: Number of Rooms with Sizes for Amenities and Facilities

Categories	Required Rooms	Required Size (m ²)	Remarks
Toilets	15	216	
Students Centre	1	240	Including FSU and other clubs for students
Health Clinic	1	60	
Canteen	1	150	10% of students at a time
Boys Common Room	1	46	
Girls Common Room	1	92	
Auditorium Hall	2		500 and 1000 capacity
Total	22	1304	Space for one auditorium of 500 capacity is estimated

			for the beginning
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9. Teachers and Staff

For various classes, the teacher student ratio as per norms and standards is given in the table 7 below.

Table 7: Norms for Number of Faculties

SN	Class	Student-teacher ratio
1	Lecture class theory (Maximum)	48:1
2	Tutorial (Maximum)	24:1
3	Lab, workshop, drawing, practical (Maximum)	24:1
4	Project work (Maximum)	12:1
5	Machine operated labs, workshop class	8:1

The ratio of professor, associate professor and assistant professor should be 1:2:4. There should be one staff for 10 students. According to this norm, the required number of faculties and staffs for conducting bachelor programs as given in Table 4.1 above, is given in Table 6.2 and Table 8 respectively.

Table 8: Tentative Number of Faculty for Running Ten Bachelor Degree Programs

SN	Department	Professor	Associate Professor	Lecturer	Instructor	Total
1	Construction Technology	3	5	10	3	21
2	Mechanical & Automation Engineering	3	5	10	2	20
3	Mechatronics	3	5	10	2	20
4	Forestry and Wood Technology	2	5	10	2	19
5	Agroforestry	3	5	10	3	21
6	Agriculture Technology	3	5	10	3	21
7	Livestock and Veterinary Technology	3	6	10	3	22
8	Medical Technology*	2	5	10	3	20
9	Clinical Technology	2	5	10	3	20
10	Himalaya Technology	3	6	10	2	21
11	Science and	3	6	10	3	22

	Humanities					
	Total	30	58	110	29	227

Table 9: Tentative Number of Non-Teaching Staff

SN	Designation	Required Number
1	Second class staff (officer)	10
2	Third class (officer)	15
3	Mukhya Karayalaya Sahaayak	25
4	Karayalaya Sahaayak	35
5	Lab boy	15
6	Karayalaya Sahayogi	18
7	Kuchikar	15
8	Chaukidar	12
	Total	145

10. Tentative Estimate for Overall Physical Infrastructure Development

Cost estimate for the construction of physical infrastructures like, administrative and academic buildings, library building, students hostel and other amenities, faculty and staff residence buildings, departments, laboratories, workshops, research units and other structures are given in the table below. (Master plan is to be included in appendix 1)

Table 10: Tentative Cost Estimate for overall Physical Infrastructure Development Plan

SN	Description	Unit in (m ²)	Required Space	Unit Cost in Thousand	Total Cost in Thousand NRs
1	Cost for administrative block		555		
	Building space for staff		534		
	Sub-total		1089	150	163,350
2	Space for faculty				
	Civil engineering department		352		
	Architecture department		176		
	Agriculture department		184		
	Mechanical department		176		
	Electrical department		161		
	Electronics & biomedical engg.		322		
	Science & humanities		176		
	Forestry		184		
	Livestock & veterinary science		184		
	Public health		161		
	Sub-total		2,076	150	311,400
3	Cost for academic blocks				
	Agriculture department block		441		
	Architecture department		441		

	Civil department block		441		
	Information Technology		441		
	Electronics and biomedical		441		
	Electrical department		441		
	Mechanical department		441		
	Science and humanities		441		
	Livestock and veterinary		441		
	Forestry and Herbal science		441		
	Sub-total		4,410	150	661,500
4	Hostel for students		6,552	115	753,480
5	Residence for faculty		9,920	115	1,140,800
6	Space for library		674	115	77,510
7	Space for laboratory		650	115	74,750
8	Carpet area for amenities		1,681	125	210,125
9	Conference hall		896	115	99,935
10	Covered hall		3,373	200	674,600
11	Research laboratory		915	115	105,225
12	Miscellaneous items	L.S			100,000
	Total	m ²	32,236		4,372,675
	Contractor's overhead & profit	15%			437,268
	VAT 13%				625,293
	Total				5,435,236
	Equipment and furniture (20%)				1,087,047
	Grand total				6,522,283

Land development cost is included in the unit cost of building construction. Cost for access road, water and sanitation, drainage system, electrification, networking and other related works within the perimeter of every block is also included in the tentative cost estimate. Total estimated amount as seen above in NRs, is around 6523 million for the overall physical infrastructure development plan of the proposed technological university. Although it looks huge amount but it can be allocated partly as per need, in consecutive annual budget of the government.

11. Salary and Allowances for Faculty and Staff

Major part of operating cost of an academic institution goes mainly in the salary and allowances of faculty and staff. While in the full fledged operation of the university, the estimated annual expenses for the salary and allowance of faculty and staff for the number shown in table 8 and 9 above is given in table 8.1 and table 8.2 below. In this heading, annual expense of NRs 13.070 crore for faculty and NRs 5.097 crore for non-teaching staff, all together NRs 18.167 crore is estimated.

Table 11: Remuneration for Faculties

SN	Department	Professor	Associate Professor	Lecturer	Instructor	Total
1	Construction	3	5	10	3	21

	Technology					
2	Urban Development	3	5	10	2	20
3	Mechatronics	3	5	10	2	20
4	Mining & Metallurgy	2	5	10	2	19
5	Agriculture Technology	3	5	10	3	21
6	Livestock and Veterinary Technology	3	5	10	3	21
7	Dairy Technology	3	6	10	3	22
8	Forestry	2	5	10	3	20
9	Medical Technology	2	5	10	3	20
10	Public Health	3	6	10	2	21
11	Science and Humanities	3	6	10	3	22
	Total	30	58	110	29	227
	Salary per month (NRs)	60,680	47,380	40,380	35,990	
	Annual salary(NRs)	23,665,200	35,724,520	57,743,400	13,568,230	130,701,350

* Reference is taken from basic salary of TU 2077.

Table 12: Remuneration for Non-Teaching Staff

SN	Designation	Required Number	Salary per Month(NRs)	Total Salary Required (NRs)
1	Second class officer	10	40,380	5,249,400
2	Section officer	15	35,990	7,018,050
3	MukhyaKarayalayaSahaayak	25	30,820	10,016,500
4	KarayalayaSahaayak	35	26,610	12,107,550
5	Lab boy	15	26,610	5,188,950
6	KarayalayaSahayogi	18	19,480	4,558,320
7	Kuchikar	15	19,480	3,798,600
8	Chaukidar	12	19,480	3,038,880
	Total:	145		50,976,250

* Reference is taken from basic salary of TU 2077.

12. Income from Students' Fees

Main source of income of an academic institution is students' fee. When the proposed ten bachelor programs run in full capacity, 480 students will be admitted each year. 10% of the total students shall be awarded scholarship and other 10% needy students shall get subsidy in tuition fee. All other students will pay NRs 50,000 per semester for tuition fee.

Total income generation from students' fee will be NRs 15.6 crore as shown in the table 9.1 below. This income will be the main source for regular operation, repair maintenance services of buildings, machineries, and for partial payment of remuneration of faculties of the university.

Table 13: Total Income from Students' Fees/year from Bachelor Level

SN	Intake	No. of student each semester	Fee for each year from 4 batches	Total income
1	Regular student (Scholarship and fee subsidy)	100	40,000	4,000,000
2	Paying student	380	400,000	152,000,000
	Total income from students			156,000,000

Apart from this the university shall generate income from research and development, trainings and consultancy services, joint ventures in possible areas with municipalities and industries, for its sustainability.

13. Conclusion

Establishment of Madan Bhandari Technological University is a priority project of the Government. The Government has mentioned in its plan and program of physical year 2077/078, article no. 68 that the necessary preparatory work for the establishment and operation of Madan Bhandari Technological University will be completed. In order to implement the stated policy and program of the government, some budget was allocated from the budget speech of 2077/078, article no.175, for the preparation of documents and legal structure of the university operation.

For this purpose, the Government of Nepal has formed Madan Bhandari Technological University Development Board (MBTU DB) on 19 Shrawan, 2077 to carry out the preparatory activities for the establishment of the University. The board has started working on the preparatory activities for the establishment of the university.

The proposed technological university will be developed gradually. In the first phase the necessary infrastructure for launching Ten Bachelor's Degree Programs in different technical areas as explained above will be developed. In the first phase of the construction, only administrative buildings of the university will be constructed and estimated budget for this work is 490 million rupees as shown in the Table 10.2 below.

In the next phase, expansion of the academic programs to Masters, Ph.D and Postgraduate degree level including additional infrastructure development will be done. In order to speed up the university erection activity, the Government is requested to take decision on: (a) Land

acquisition (b) Approval of MBTU Bill (c) Budget allocation for infrastructure development in annual basis through UGC as per need, as shown in the Table 7.1 above.

First Phase of Infrastructure Development

In the first phase of infrastructure development, the construction of administrative blocks of the university with spaces as shown in Table 10.1 is planned. For the administrative facility of the university as shown below, a total of 1677 square meter of floor area is required.

Table 14: Number of Rooms with Sizes for Administrative Facilities

Categories	Required Rooms	Required size (m ²)
Vice chancellor	2	40
Rector	1	20
Registrar	1	20
Dean	2	40
Campus Chief	1	20
Asst. Campus Chief	3	45
Head of departments	7	105
Administration Section	3	60
Account Section	3	45
Examination Section	3	60
Procurement Section/ Main store	3	45
Liaison office room	1	15
Reception lounge	1	20
Registration/Record Room	1	20
Prof/Associate Professors Rooms	6	528
Teachers Room	6	534
Department offices	6	60
Total	50	1677

Table 15: Tentative Cost Estimate for Construction of Administrative Blocks

SN	Description	Unit in (m ²)	Required Space	Unit Cost in Thousand NRs	Total Cost in Thousand NRs
1	Administrative blocks		555	150	83,250
2	Building space for staff		534	150	80,100
3	Building space for department office, teachers and professors rooms as shown above		588	150	88,200
	Sub-total		1677	150	251,550

The unit cost shown above for administrative buildings construction includes land development cost, cost for access road, water and sanitation, drainage system, electrification, networking and other related works within the perimeter of every block. Total estimated amount for the construction of administrative blocks with spaces shown above in NRs, is around 252 million.